

Article

Neutrosophic Triplet Non-Associative Semihypergroups with Application

Muhammad Gulistan ¹

¹ Department of Mathematics & Statistics, Hazara University, Mansehra 21130, Pakistan; gulistanmath@hu.edu.pk (M.G.); shahnawazawan82@gmail.com (S.N.)

² School of Mathematical Sciences, Faculty of Science and Technology, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 UKM Bangi Selangor DE, Malaysia

* Correspondence: nas@ukm.edu.my; Tel.: +60-1-9214-5750

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

Received: 8 October 2018; Accepted: 27 October 2018; Published: 8 November 2018

Abstract: In this paper, we extended the idea of a neutrosophic triplet set to non-associative semihypergroups and define neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. We discuss some basic results and properties. At the end, we provide an application of the proposed structure in Football.

Keywords: \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroups; neutrosophic triplet set; neutro-homomorphism

1. Introduction

The study of origin and features of neutralities lies in the scope of a new branch of philosophy known as Neutrosophy. In 1995, Smarandache (for the first time) used the idea of Neutrosophy and developed neutrosophic logic which is a more practical and realistic approach, to handle imprecise and vague information. He introduced the concept of (T-truth, I-indeterminacy, F-falsity) memberships. According to Smarandache Neutrosophic, logics generalizes the all previous logics such as fuzzy logic [1], intuitionistic fuzzy logic [2] and interval valued fuzzy logic [3]. Kandasamy and Smarandache [4] developed many neutrosophic algebraic structures, neutrosophic bigroup, neutrosophic vector space, neutrosophic groups and so on, based on neutrosophic logic. For practical applications, we refer the readers to [5–9]. For neutrosophic triplet sets, we refer the readers [10–13]. In 2016, Smarandache and Ali [14] gave the concept of Neutrosophic triplet groups which is a very useful addition in the theory of groups.

Hyperstructure theory was brought-out by Marty [15] in 1934, when he defined hypergroup, set about analyzing their properties and exerted them to a group. Several papers and books have been compiled in this direction, see references [16–18]. In 1990, in Greece, a congress was organized by Thomas Vougiouklis on hyperstructure, which was first named algebraic hyper structures and its applications algebraic hyper structures(AHA); however actually was the fourth, because there had been three more congresses in Italy by Corsini, on the same topic but random names. During this congress, Vougiouklis [19] presented the concept of weak structure, presently known as Hv-structure. A number of writers have gone through various aspects of Hv-structure. For instance, references [20–27]. Another book by Davvaz and Fotea in 2007 has been devoted especially to the study of hyperring theory [28].

Kazim and Naseeruddin [29] in 1970, presented the concept of left almost semigroups (\mathcal{LA} -semigroups) and shifted the discussion toward non-associative structures. According to them, a groupoid S is called \mathcal{LA} -semigroups, if it satisfies the left invertive law: $(w_1 w_2) w_3 = (w_3 w_2) w_1$ for all $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S$. After that, researchers started working in this direction such as, references [30–32] and Yusuf gave the idea of left almost rings [33]. Hila and Dine [34] in 2011, shifted the non-associative structures to non-associative hyperstructures and furnished the idea of \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup, which

is generalization of semigroup, semihypergroup, \mathcal{LA} -semigroup by using left invertive law with the help of Marty's hyperoperation. Yaqoob et al. [35] expanded the work of Hila and Dine. Yousafzai et al. in [36] and Amjad et al. [37] tried to generalize different aspects of left almost semihypergroups. The concept of Hv- \mathcal{LA} -semigroup was laid by Gulistan et al. [38] in 2015. The idea of partially ordered left almost semihypergroups was developed by Naveed et al. [39] in 2015. Rehman et al. [40], initiated the study of \mathcal{LA} -hyperrings and discussed its hyperideals and hypersystems in 2017. Nawaz et al. introduced the concept of left almost semihyperrings [41]. Yaqoob et al. [42] gave the idea of left almost polygroups in 2018.

In this paper, we extended the idea of neutrosophic triplet set to non-associative semihypergroups. We define neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. In neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup every element " w " has left neut(w) and left anti(w). In neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup left neut(w) of an element " w " may or may not be equal to left identity. We also defined the neutro-homomorphism on \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroups. At the end, we present an application of the proposed structure in football.

2. Preliminaries

This section of paper consists of some basic definitions, which are directly used in our work.

Definition 1 ([34]). Let \mathcal{H} be a non void set and $\circ : \mathcal{H} * \mathcal{H} \rightarrow P^*(\mathcal{H})$ be a hyperoperation, where $P^*(\mathcal{H})$ is the family non-void subset of \mathcal{H} . The pair $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is called hypergroupoid.

For any two non-void subsets W_1 and W_2 of \mathcal{H} , then

$$W_1 * W_2 = \bigcup_{w_1 \in W_1, w_2 \in W_2} w_1 * w_2.$$

Definition 2 ([34]). An \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup is the hypergroupoid $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ with

$$(w_1 * w_2) * w_3 = (w_3 * w_2) * w_1 \quad (1)$$

for all, $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathcal{H}$. The equation (1) is called left invertive law.

Definition 3 ([35]). An element e of an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup \mathcal{H} is called left identity (resp., pure left identity) if for all $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, $w_1 \in e * w_1$ (resp., $w_1 = e * w_1$). An element e of an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup \mathcal{H} is called right identity (resp., pure right identity) if for all $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, $w_1 \in w_1 * e$ (resp., $w_1 = e * w_1$). An element e of an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup \mathcal{H} is called identity (resp., pure right identity) if for all $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, $w_1 \in w_1 * e \cap e * w_1$ (resp., $w_1 = w_1 * e \cap e * w_1$).

Definition 4 ([35]). An \mathcal{LA} -smihypergroup with pure left identity satisfies the following property

$$w_1 * (w_2 * w_3) = w_2 * (w_1 * w_3).$$

Definition 5 ([14]). Let N be a non-void set with a binary operation $*$ and $w_1 \in N$. Then w_1 is said to be neutrosophic triplet if there exist an element neut(w_1) $\in N$ such that

$$w_1 * \text{neut}(w_1) = \text{neut}(w_1) * w_1 = w_1,$$

where neut(w_1) is different from unity element. Also there exist anti(w_1) $\in N$ such that

$$w_1 * \text{anti}(w_1) = \text{anti}(w_1) * w_1 = \text{neut}(w_1).$$

If there are more anti(w_1)'s for a given w_1 , one takes that anti(w_1) = w_2 that anti(w_1) in its turn forms a neutrosophic triplet, i.e., there exists neut(w_2) and anti(w_2). We denote the neutrosophic triplet w_1 by $(w_1, \text{neut}(w_1), \text{anti}(w_1))$. By neut(w_1), we means neutral of w_1 .

Example 1 ([14]). Consider Z_6 under multiplication modulo 6. Then 2 is a neutrosophic triplet, because $neut(2) = 4$, as $2 \times 4 = 8$. Similarly $anti(2) = 2$ because $2 \times 2 = 4$. Thus 2 is a neutrosophic triplet, which is denoted by $(2, 4, 2)$. Similarly 4 is a neutrosophic triplet because $neut(4) = anti(4) = 4$. So 4 is represented by as $(4, 4, 4)$. 3 is not a neutrosophic triplet as $neut(3) = 5$ but $anti(3)$ does not exist in Z_6 and 0 is a trivial neutrosophic triplet as $neut(0) = anti(0) = 0$. This is denoted by $(0, 0, 0)$.

3. Neutrosophic Triplet \mathcal{LA} -Semihypergroups

In this section, we defined the neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup and some results on neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup are provided.

Definition 6. Let \mathcal{H} be a non void set with a binary hyperoperation $*$ and $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$. Then \mathcal{H} is called

1. left neutrosophic triplet set if for every $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, there exist $neut(w_1)$ and $anti(w_1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 &\in neut(w_1) * w_1, \\neut(w_1) &\in anti(w_1) * w_1.\end{aligned}$$

2. right neutrosophic triplet set if for every $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, there exist $neut(w_1)$ and $anti(w_1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 &\in w_1 * neut(w_1), \\neut(w_1) &\in w_1 * anti(w_1).\end{aligned}$$

3. neutrosophic triplet set if for every $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, there exist $neut(w_1)$ and $anti(w_1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 &\in (neut(w_1) * w_1) \cap (w_1 * neut(w_1)), \\neut(w_1) &\in (anti(w_1) * w_1) \cap (w_1 * anti(w_1)).\end{aligned}$$

Definition 7. Let \mathcal{H} be a set with a binary hyperoperation $*$ and $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$. Then \mathcal{H} is called

1. pure left neutrosophic triplet set if for every $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, there exist $neut(w_1)$ and $anti(w_1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 &= neut(w_1) * w_1, \\neut(w_1) &= anti(w_1) * w_1.\end{aligned}$$

2. pure right neutrosophic triplet set if for every $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, there exist $neut(w_1)$ and $anti(w_1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 &= w_1 * neut(w_1), \\neut(w_1) &= w_1 * anti(w_1).\end{aligned}$$

3. pure neutrosophic triplet set if for every $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, there exist $neut(w_1)$ and $anti(w_1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 &= (neut(w_1) * w_1) \cap (w_1 * neut(w_1)), \\neut(w_1) &= (anti(w_1) * w_1) \cap (w_1 * anti(w_1)).\end{aligned}$$

Example 2. Let $\mathcal{H} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$ be a se with hyperoperation defined as follows:

*	w_1	w_2	w_3
w_1	w_3	$\{w_1, w_2\}$	w_1
w_2	$\{w_1, w_2\}$	$\{w_1, w_2\}$	$\{w_1, w_3\}$
w_3	w_2	$\{w_1, w_3\}$	w_2

A Cayley table 1

Here (w_1, w_2, w_2) , (w_2, w_2, w_2) and (w_3, w_2, w_3) are neutrosophic triplets.

Definition 8. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a left (resp., right, left pure, right pure) neutrosophic triplet set. Then \mathcal{H} is called left (resp., right, left pure, right pure) neutrosophic triplet $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{A}$ -semihypergroup, if the following conditions are satisfied:

1. $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is well defined.
2. $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ satisfies the left invertive law.

Example 3. Let $\mathcal{H} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5\}$ be a set with the hyperoperation defined as follows:

*	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5
w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1
w_2	w_1	$\{w_3, w_5\}$	w_3	$\{w_1, w_4\}$	$\{w_3, w_5\}$
w_3	w_1	w_3	w_3	$\{w_1, w_4\}$	w_3
w_4	w_1	$\{w_1, w_4\}$	$\{w_1, w_4\}$	w_4	$\{w_1, w_4\}$
w_5	w_1	$\{w_2, w_5\}$	w_3	$\{w_1, w_4\}$	$\{w_2, w_5\}$

A Cayley table 2

Here $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is an $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{A}$ -semihypergroup, as the element of \mathcal{H} satisfies the left invertive law. Here (w_1, w_1, w_1) , (w_2, w_5, w_5) , (w_3, w_3, w_3) , (w_4, w_4, w_4) and (w_5, w_2, w_5) are left neutrosophic triplets. Hence $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a left neutrosophic triplet $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{A}$ -semihypergroup.

Definition 9. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be neutrosophic (resp., pure neutrosophic) triplet set. Then \mathcal{H} is said to be neutrosophic (resp., pure neutrosophic) triplet $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{A}$ -semihypergroup, if the following condition are satisfied:

1. $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a well defined.
2. $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ satisfies the left invertive law.

Example 4. Let $\mathcal{H} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$ and the hyperoperation defined in the table as follows:

*	w_1	w_2	w_3
w_1	$\{w_1, w_2\}$	$\{w_1, w_2\}$	w_3
w_2	\mathcal{H}	\mathcal{H}	w_3
w_3	w_3	w_3	w_3

A Cayley table 3

Here $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup, as the element of \mathcal{H} satisfies the left invertive law. Here (w_1, w_2, w_1) , (w_2, w_1, w_2) and (w_3, w_3, w_3) are neutrosophic triplets. Hence $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup.

Remark 1. $Neut(w_2)$ of an element " w_2 " is not unique under the hyperoperation $*$ in \mathcal{H} and depend on elements and hyperoperation. By the Example 4 $neut(w_2) = w_1, w_2$. Similarly $anti(w_2) = w_1, w_2$ of an element " w_2 " is not unique and depends on the element and the hyperoperation $*$.

Remark 2. Left neut of an element is could be different from left identity.

Definition 10. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. An element $w_1 \in \mathcal{H}$, then there exist pure left $neut(w_1)$ such that $w_1 = neut(w_1) * w_1$ and pure left $anti(w_1)$ such that $neut(w_1) = anti(w_1) * w_1$.

Proposition 1. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure left neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup with pure left identity. Then $w_2 * w_1 = w_3 * w_1$ if and only if

$$neut(w_1) * w_2 = neut(w_1) * w_3.$$

Proof. Suppose that $w_2 * w_3 = w_3 * w_1$ for $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathcal{H}$. Since $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a pure left neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} semihypergroup, so $anti(w_1) \in \mathcal{H}$. Multiply $anti(w_1)$ to the right side of $w_2 * w_1 = w_3 * w_1$

$$\begin{aligned}(w_2 * w_1) * anti(w_1) &= (w_3 * w_1) * anti(w_1) \\ (anti(a) * w_1) * w_2 &= (anti(w_1) * w_1) * w_3 \\ neut(w_1) * w_2 &= neut(w_1) * w_3.\end{aligned}$$

Conversely, let $neut(w_1) * w_2 = neut(w_1) * w_3$. Multiply to both right sides by w_1

$$\begin{aligned}neut(w_1) * (w_2 * w_1) &= neut(w_1) * (w_3 * w_1) \\ w_2 * (neut(w_1) * w_1) &= w_3 * (neut(w_1) * w_1) \\ w_2 * w_1 &= w_3 * w_1.\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Proposition 2. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure right neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup with pure left identity. Then $w_2 * neut(w_1) = w_3 * neut(w_1)$ if $w_2 * anti(w_1) = w_3 * anti(w_1)$ for all $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathcal{H}$.

Proof. Suppose $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a pure right neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup with pure left identity and $w_2 * anti(w_1) = w_3 * anti(w_1)$ for $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathcal{H}$. Multiply w_1 to the left side of $w_2 * anti(w_1) = w_3 * anti(w_1)$,

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 * (w_2 * anti(w_1)) &= w_1 * (w_3 * anti(w_1)) \\ w_2 * (w_1 * anti(w_1)) &= w_3 * (w_1 * anti(w_1)) \\ w_2 * neut(w_1) &= w_3 * neut(w_1) \quad (\text{because } neut(w_1) = w_1 * anti(w_1)).\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$w_2 * neut(w_1) = w_3 * neut(w_1).$$

\square

Proposition 3. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure right neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Then $neut(w_1) * w_2 = neut(w_1) * w_3$ if $w_2 * anti(w_1) = w_3 * anti(w_1)$ for all $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathcal{H}$.

Proof. Suppose $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a pure right neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup and $w_2 * anti(w_1) = w_3 * anti(w_1)$ for $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in \mathcal{H}$. Multiply w_1 to the right side of $w_2 * anti(w_1) = w_3 * anti(w_1)$,

$$\begin{aligned}(w_2 * anti(w_1)) * w_1 &= (w_3 * anti(w_1)) * w_1 \\ (w_1 * anti(w_1)) * w_2 &= (w_1 * anti(w_1)) * w_3 \\ neut(w_1) * w_2 &= neut(w_1) * w_3 \quad (\text{because } neut(w_1) = w_1 * anti(w_1)).\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$neut(w_1) * w_2 = neut(w_1) * w_3.$$

□

Theorem 1. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure right neutrosophic triplet idempotent \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Then $neut(w_1) * neut(w_1) = neut(w_1)$.

Proof. Consider $neut(w_1) * neut(w_1) = neut(w_1)$. Multiply first with w_1 to the right and then again multiply with w_1 to the right, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}((neut(w_1) * neut(w_1)) * w_1) * w_1 &= (neut(w_1) * w_1) * w_1 \\ ((w_1 * neut(w_1)) * neut(w_1)) * w_1 &= (w_1 * w_1) * neut(w_1) \\ (w_1 * neut(w_1)) * (w_1 * neut(w_1)) &= w_1 * neut(w_1) \\ w_1 * w_1 &= w_1 \\ w_1 &= w_1.\end{aligned}$$

This shows that

$$neut(w_1) * neut(w_1) = neut(w_1).$$

□

Theorem 2. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure right neutrosophic triplet idempotent \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup with pure left identity. Then $neut(w_1) * anti(w_1) = anti(w_1)$.

Proof. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure right neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup with pure left identity. Multiply w_1 to the left of both side $neut(w_1) * anti(w_1) = anti(w_1)$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}w_1 * ((neut(w_1) * anti(w_1)) &= w_1 * anti(w_1) \\ neut(w_1) * (w_1 * anti(w_1)) &= neut(w_1) \\ neut(w_1) * neut(w_1) &= neut(w_1) \\ neut(w_1) &= neut(w_1) \quad (\text{By Theorem 1})\end{aligned}$$

This shows that

$$neut(w_1) * anti(w_1) = anti(w_1).$$

□

Theorem 3. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure right neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Then

1. $neut(w_1) * neut(w_2) = neut(w_1 * w_2)$ for all $w_1, w_2 \in \mathcal{H}$.
2. $anti(w_1) * anti(w_2) = anti(w_1 * w_2)$ for all $w_1, w_2 \in \mathcal{H}$.

Proof. 1. Consider the left hand side $neut(w_1) * neut(w_2)$. Multiply first with w_2 to the right and then again multiply with w_1 to the right, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} ((neut(w_1) * neut(w_2)) * w_2) * w_1 &= ((w_2 * neut(w_2)) * neut(w_1)) * w_1 \\ &= (w_2 * neut(w_1)) * w_1 \\ &= (w_1 * neut(w_1)) * w_2 \\ &= w_1 * w_2. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$((neut(w_1) * neut(w_2)) * w_2) * w_1 = w_1 * w_2 \quad (2)$$

Now consider the right side $neut(w_1 * w_2)$. Multiply first with w_2 to the right and then again multiply with w_1 to the right, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} (neut(w_1 * w_2) * w_2) * w_1 &= (w_1 * w_2) * neut(w_1 * w_2) \\ &= w_1 * w_2. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$(neut(w_1 * w_2) * w_2) * w_1 = w_1 * w_2 \quad (3)$$

From the Equations (2) and (3) it is clear that $neut(w_1) * neut(w_2) = neut(w_1 * w_2)$.

2. Consider the left hand side $anti(w_1) * anti(w_2)$. Multiply first with w_2 to the right and then again multiply with w_1 to the right, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} ((anti(w_1) * anti(w_2)) * w_2) * w_1 &= ((w_2 * anti(w_2)) * anti(w_1)) * w_1 \\ &= (neut(w_2) * anti(w_1)) * w_1 \\ &= (w_1 * anti(w_1)) * neut(w_2) \\ &= neut(w_1) * neut(w_2) \\ &= neut(w_1 * w_2). \end{aligned}$$

So

$$((anti(w_1) * anti(w_2)) * w_2) * w_1 = neut(w_1 * w_2) \quad (4)$$

Now consider the right side $anti(w_1 * w_2)$. Multiply first with w_2 to the right and then again multiply with w_1 to the right, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} (anti(w_1 * w_2) * w_2) * w_1 &= (w_1 * w_2) * anti(w_1 * w_2) \\ &= neut(w_1 * w_2) \end{aligned}$$

So

$$(anti(w_1 * w_2) * w_2) * w_1 = neut(w_1 * w_2) \quad (5)$$

From the Equations (4) and (5) it is clear that

$$anti(w_1) * anti(w_2) = anti(w_1 * w_2).$$

□

In the following example, we show that in a left neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup

$$neut(w_1) * neut(w_2) \neq neut(w_1 * w_2) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } anti(w_1) * anti(w_2) \neq anti(w_1 * w_2). \quad (7)$$

Example 5. Let $\mathcal{H} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}$ be a set with the hyperoperation defined as follow

*	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4
w_1	$\{w_1, w_3, w_4\}$	$\{w_2, w_4\}$	\mathcal{H}	\mathcal{H}
w_2	$\{w_1, w_2, w_4\}$	$\{w_1, w_2\}$	$\{w_2, w_4\}$	$\{w_2, w_3, w_4\}$
w_3	$\{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_1, w_3, w_4\}$	$\{w_2, w_4\}$	$\{w_2, w_3, w_4\}$
w_4	\mathcal{H}	$\{w_2, w_3, w_4\}$	\mathcal{H}	$\{w_1, w_3\}$

A Cayley table 4

All the elements of \mathcal{H} satisfies the left invertive law. Here (w_1, w_3, w_4) , (w_2, w_4, w_1) , (w_3, w_1, w_4) and (w_4, w_2, w_3) are left neutrosophic triplets. Hence $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a left neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Now

$$\begin{aligned} \text{neut}(w_1) * \text{neut}(w_2) &\neq \text{neut}(w_1 * w_2) \\ w_3 * w_4 &\neq \text{neut}(\{w_2, w_4\}) \\ \{w_2, w_3, w_4\} &\neq \text{neut}(w_2) \cup \text{neut}(w_4) \\ \{w_2, w_3, w_4\} &\neq \{w_2, w_4\}. \end{aligned}$$

Also

$$\begin{aligned} \text{anti}(w_1) * \text{anti}(w_2) &\neq \text{anti}(w_1 * w_2) \\ w_4 * w_1 &\neq \text{anti}(\{w_2, w_4\}) \\ \mathcal{H} &\neq \text{anti}(w_2) \cup \text{anti}(w_4) \\ \mathcal{H} &\neq \{w_1, w_3\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence this shows that $\text{neut}(w_1) * \text{neut}(w_2) \neq \text{neut}(w_1 * w_2)$ and $\text{anti}(w_1) * \text{anti}(w_2) \neq \text{anti}(w_1 * w_2)$.

Theorem 4. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure left neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Then $\text{neut}(\text{anti}(w_1)) = \text{neut}(w_1)$.

Proof. Let $\text{neut}(\text{anti}(w_1)) = \text{neut}(w_1)$. If we put $\text{anti}(w_1) = w_2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{neut}(w_2) &= \text{neut}(w_1). \text{ Post multiply by } w_2 \\ \text{neut}(w_2) * w_2 &= \text{neut}(w_1) * w_2 \\ w_2 &= \text{neut}(w_1) * w_2 \\ \text{anti}(w_1) &= \text{neut}(w_1) * \text{anti}(w_1), \text{ as } w_2 = \text{anti}(w_1) \\ \text{anti}(w_1) &= \text{anti}(w_1). \text{ By Theorem 1 } \text{neut}(w_1) * \text{anti}(w_1) = \text{anti}(w_1) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\text{neut}(\text{anti}(w_1)) = \text{neut}(w_1)$. \square

Theorem 5. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a pure left neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Then $\text{anti}(\text{anti}(w_1)) = w_1$.

Proof. Consider $anti(anti(w_1)) = w_1$. Post multiplying both sides $anti(w_1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 anti(anti(w_1)) * anti(w_1) &= w_1 * anti(w_1) \\
 neut(anti(w_1)) &= (neut(w_1) * w_1) * anti(w_1) \\
 neut(anti(w_1)) &= (anti(w_1) * w_1) * neut(w_1) \text{ by left invertive law} \\
 neut(anti(w_1)) &= neut(w_1) * neut(w_1) \\
 neut(anti(w_1)) &= neut(w_1) \text{ by Theorem 1 } neut(w_1) * neut(w_1) = neut(w_1) \\
 neut(w_1) &= neut(w_1) \text{ by Theorem 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $anti(anti(w_1)) = w_1$. \square

Definition 11. Let $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ be a neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup and let K be a subset of \mathcal{H} . Then, K is called neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -subsemihypergroup, if K itself is a neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup.

Example 6. Let $\mathcal{H} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5\}$ be a set with the hyperoperation defined in the table as follow

*	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4	w_5
w_1	$\{w_1, w_3\}$	w_2	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_4, w_5\}$	w_5
w_2	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_4, w_5\}$	w_5
w_3	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_2, w_3\}$	$\{w_4, w_5\}$	w_5
w_4	$\{w_4, w_5\}$	$\{w_4, w_5\}$	$\{w_4, w_5\}$	w_4	w_5
w_5	w_5	w_5	w_5	w_5	w_5

A Cayley table 5

Here $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup, because the element of \mathcal{H} satisfies the left invertive law. Here $(w_1, w_1, w_1), (w_2, w_3, w_3), (w_3, w_2, w_3), (w_4, w_4, w_4)$ and (w_5, w_4, w_4) are neutrosophic triplet. Hence $(\mathcal{H}, *)$ is a neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Let $K = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$ be subset of \mathcal{H} . As K is a neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup under the $*$. Then K is called neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{H} .

Lemma 1. Let K be a non-empty subset of a neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup \mathcal{H} . The following are equivalent.

1. K is a neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup.
2. For all $w_1, w_2 \in K, w_1 * w_2 \in K$.

Proof. The proof is straightforward. \square

Definition 12. Let $(\mathcal{H}_1, *_1)$ and $(\mathcal{H}_2, *_2)$ are two neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroups. Let $f : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_2$ be a mapping. Then f is called neutro-homomorphism if for all $w_1, w_2 \in \mathcal{H}_1$, we have

1. $f(w_1 *_1 w_2) = f(w_2) *_2 f(w_1),$
2. $f(neut(w_1)) = neut(f(w_1)),$
3. $f(anti(w_1)) = anti(f(w_1)).$

Theorem 6. Let $f : \mathcal{H}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_2$ be a neutro-homomorphism. Where \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 are two neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup. Let

1. The image of f is a neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{H}_2 .

2. The inverse image of f is a neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{H}_1 .

Proof. The proof is straightforward. \square

Remark 3. We have the following key points;

1. Every neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup is an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup, but the reverse may or may not true.
2. In neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup, every element must have a left $neut(\cdot)$, but in an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup the left $neut(\cdot)$ of an element may or may not exist.
3. In neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup, every element must have left $anti(\cdot)$, but in an \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup the element may or may not have semihypergroup.
4. In neutrosophic \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup pure left $neut(\cdot)$ is not equal to pure left Identity.

4. Application

Neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroups has many applications in different areas. Here, we present an application of neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup in football. We can use different versions of neut and anti elements like left, right, pure left and pure right that we may see in different situations. The interesting prospect of this newly defined structure is that it is not comutative, so any change from the left and same types of change from the righth of a certain element may affect the final results with respect to neut and anti.

Consider a Football team; the centre midfield player " C_m " having a degree of performance d_1 . The players " C_{ml2} " and " C_{mr1} " are the midfield player having degree of performance d_1 . Thus using Definition 6, the $neut(C_m) \in \{C_{ml2}, C_{mr1}\}$. The players " C_{ml1} " and " C_{mr2} " are having better degree of performance d_2 , thus using Definition 6, the $neut(C_m) \in anti(C_m) * C_m \cap C_m * anti(C_m) = C_{ml1} * C_m \cap C_m * C_{mr2} = \{d_1, d_2\}$ Neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup can help the coach to select the players for filling the position in the playground, when a player gets injured. The major advantage of neutrosophic triplet \mathcal{LA} -semihypergroup is that if we have a centre mid player and this player has the other players having the same performance on the right side as neut of it and it has one player on the left having better performance than it as shown in the following Figure 1.

If the performance of a player playing on the left side and right side of a centre mid player is equal to performance of a centre mid player then the structure reduces to a duplet structure. Similarly, we can find many applications in different directions.

Figure 1. A view of football match.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we apply the idea of neutrosophic triplet sets at the very useful non-associative hyperstructures, namely $\mathcal{L}\mathcal{A}$ -semihypergroups. We define neutrosophic triplet set (left, right, pure left, pure right). We discuss some basic results and an application of the proposed structure at the end. In future, we are aiming to extend this idea and give more interesting results.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed equally.

Funding: Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia- Grant No. GUP-2017-105.

Acknowledgments: We are indebted to Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia for providing financial support under the grant GUP-2017-105, and authors are highly grateful to referees for their valuable comments and suggestions.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Smarandache, F. *A Unifying Field in Logics. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Probability, Set and Logic*; Rehoboth American Research Press: Rehoboth, NM, USA, 1999.
2. Kandasamy, W.B.V.; Smarandache, F. *Some Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures and Neutrosophic N-Algebraic Structures*; Hexis: Phoenix, AZ, USA, 2006; p. 219.
3. Kandasamy, W.B.V.; Smarandache, F. *N-Algebraic Structures And S-N-Algebraic Structures*; Hexis: Phoenix, AZ, USA, 2006; p. 209.
4. Kandasamy, W.B.V.; Smarandache, F. *Basic Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures and Their Applications to Fuzzy and Neutrosophic Models*; Hexis: Phoenix, AZ, USA, 2004; p. 149.
5. Al-Quran, A.; Hassan, N. The complex neutrosophic soft expert set and its application in decision making. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.* **2018**, *34*, 569–582. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Al-Quran, A.; Hassan, N. The complex neutrosophic soft expert relation and its multiple attribute decision-making method. *Entropy* **2018**, *20*, 101. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Abu Qamar, M.; Hassan, N. Q-neutrosophic soft relation and its application in decision making. *Entropy* **2018**, *20*, 172.
8. Abu Qamar, M.; Hassan, N. Entropy, measures of distance and similarity of Q-neutrosophic soft sets and some applications. *Entropy* **2018**, *20*, 672.
9. Uluçay, V.; Sahin, M.; Hassan, N. Generalized neutrosophic soft expert set for multiple-criteria decision-making. *Symmetry* **2018**, *10*, 437. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Smarandache, F. *Neutrosophic Perspectives: Triplets, Duplets, Multisets, Hybrid Operators, Modal Logic, Hedge Algebras. And Applications*; Pons Publishing House: Brussels, Belgium, 2017.
11. Zhang, X.H.; Smarandache, F.; Liang, X.L. Neutrosophic duplet semi-group and cancellable neutrosophic triplet groups. *Symmetry* **2017**, *9*, 275. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Bal, M.; Shalla, M.M.; Olgun, N. Neutrosophic triplet cosets and quotient groups. *Symmetry* **2018**, *10*, 126. [[CrossRef](#)]
13. Jaiyeola, T.G.; Smarandache, F. Some results on neutrosophic triplet group and their applications. *Symmetry* **2018**, *10*, 202. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Smarandache, F.; Ali, M. Neutrosophic triplet group. *Neural Comput. Appl.* **2018**, *29*, 595–601. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Marty, F. Sur une generalization de la notion de groupe. In Proceedings of the 8th Congres des Mathematicians Scandinaves, Stockholm, Sweden, 1934; pp. 45–49.
16. Corsini, P. *Prolegomena of Hypergroup Theory*; Aviani Editore: Udine, Italy, 1993.
17. Vougiouklis, T. *Hyperstructures and Their Representations*; Hadronic Press: Palm Harbor, FL, USA, 1994.
18. Corsini, P.; Leoreanu, V. *Applications of Hyperstructure Theory*; Kluwer Academic: Dordrecht, The Netherlands, 2003.
19. Vougiouklis, T. A new class of hyperstructures. *J. Comb. Inf. Syst. Sci.* **1995**, *20*, 229–235.
20. Vougiouklis, T. ∂ -operations and Hv-fields. *Acta Math. Sin. (Engl. Ser.)* **2008**, *24*, 1067–1078. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Vougiouklis, T. *The h/v-Structures, Algebraic Hyperstructures and Applications*; Taru Publications: New Delhi, India, 2004; pp. 115–123.
22. Spartalis, S. On Hv-semigroups. *Ital. J. Pure Appl. Math.* **2002**, *11*, 165–174.

23. Spartalis, S. On reversible Hv-group. In Proceedings of the 5th International Congress on Algebraic Hyperstructures and Applications, Jasi, Romania, 4–10 July 1993; pp. 163–170.
24. Vougiouklis, T. The fundamental relation in hyperrings: The general hyperfield. In Proceedings of the Algebraic Hyperstructures and Applications, Xanthi, Greece, April 1991; pp. 203–211.
25. Spartalis, S. Quotients of P-Hv-rings. In *New Frontiers in Hyperstructures*; Hadronic Press: Palm Harbor, FL, USA, 1996; pp. 167–176.
26. Spartalis, S.; Vougiouklis, T. The fundamental relations on Hv-rings. *Riv. Mat. Pura Appl.* **1994**, *7*, 7–20.
27. Spartalis, S. On the number of Hv-rings with P-hyperoperations. *Discret. Math.* **1996**, *155*, 225–231. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Davvaz, B.; Fotea, V.L. *Hyperring Theory and Applications*; International Academic Press: New York, NY, USA, 2007.
29. Kazim, M.A.; Naseerudin, N. On almost semigroups. *Aligarh Bull. Math.* **1972**, *2*, 41–47.
30. Kamran, M.S. Conditions for LA-Semigroups to Resemble Associative Structures. Ph.D. Thesis, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan, 1993.
31. Protic, P.V.; Stevanovic, N. AG-test and some general properties of Abel-Grassmann's groupoids. *Pure Math. Appl.* **1995**, *6*, 371–383.
32. Protic, P.V.; Stevanovic, N. The structural theorem for AG^* -groupoids. *Ser. Math. Inform.* **1995**, *10*, 25–33.
33. Yusuf, S.M. On Left Almost Ring. In Proceedings of the 7th International Pure Mathematics Conference, Islamabad, Pakistan, 5–7 August 2006.
34. Hila, K.; Dine, J. On hyperideals in left almost semihypergroups. *ISRN Algebra* **2011**, *2011*, 953124. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Yaqoob, N.; Corsini, P.; Yousafzai, F. On intra-regular left almost semihypergroups with pure left identity. *J. Math.* **2013**, *2013*, 510790. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Yousafzai, F.; Hila, K.; Corsini, P.; Zeb, A. Existence of non-associative algebraic hyperstructures and related problems. *Afr. Mat.* **2015**, *26*, 981–995. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Amjad, V.; Hila, K.; Yousafzai, F. Generalized hyperideals in locally associative left almost semihypergroups. *N. Y. J. Math.* **2014**, *20*, 1063–1076.
38. Gulistan, M.; Yaqoob, N.; Shahzad, M. A Note On Hv-LA-semigroup. *UPB Sci. Bull. Ser. A* **2015**, *77*, 93–106.
39. Yaqoob, N.; Gulistan, M. Partially ordered left almost semihypergroups. *J. Egypt. Math. Soc.* **2015**, *23*, 231–235. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Rehman, I.; Yaqoob, N.; Nawaz, S. Hyperideals and hypersystems in LA-hyperrings. *Songklanakarin J. Sci. Technol.* **2017**, *39*, 651–657.
41. Nawaz, S.; Rehman, I.; Gulistan, M. On left almost semihyperrings. *Int. J. Anal. Appl.* **2018**, *16*, 528–541.
42. Yaqoob, N.; Cristea, I.; Gulistan, M.; Nawaz, S. Left almost polygroups. *Ital. J. Pure Appl. Math.* **2018**, *39*, 465–474.

© 2018 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).